

AGRIFOODTEF DATASPACE
(TECHNOLOGICAL ENABLERS FOR IMPLEMENTATION)

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Abstract

This reports an update on the Y2 activities of the development of the AgrifoodTEF dataspace, a distributed collection of datasets created during the execution of testing and validation services, which will be amongst the assets the project will use for its sustainability plan.

The deliverable explores the key building blocks of Dataspaces, examines common technologies like Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC), Pontus-X, and Gaia-X to establish secure and interoperable environments that encourage data sharing, while maintaining data sovereignty for data controllers/producers. It introduces the advantages of compute-to-data approaches as additional data sovereignty guarantees. The report then focuses on the AgriFoodTEF Dataspace implementation, outlining onboarding procedures, digital wallet setup, data asset acquisition and consumption, data publishing and governance mechanisms, all needed enablers for the creation of a business viable asset. Finally, it presents some concrete use cases where some AgrifoodTEF Partners have started producing datasets expected to be valorised through a dataspace compliant implementation with the aim of fostering a data-driven agricultural transformation aligned with EU policies.

1. Foreword and summary of the previous deliverable

A data space is a federated data ecosystem governed by shared rules and policies, allowing participants secure, transparent, and trusted access to data in a unified manner. The main motivation behind dataspace in the agrifood sector is to create enlarged datasets for effectively training AI algorithms, proposing the right enablers that allow data sharing to be addressed through the setup of trustworthy environments, giving support for data-sovereignty for the data controllers (as per Data Governance Act definition), enabling them to valorize those data and algorithms, and keep control over the use of it in any data-exchange situation.

In a previous deliverable, we have highlighted the rationale for the choice made to use data spaces and illustrated the necessary technical and administrative building blocks and standards from a generic point of view before exploring the specific requirements and planning implementations that are specific to the AgrifoodTEF project. Here we take a step further and illustrate what was achieved during the second year of execution. Setting up such infrastructure as a federation between TEF partners across different nodes and satellite locations in Europe is challenging. However, we expect that exploiting the existing technologies will also produce benefits for AgrifoodTEF and its participants, laying the foundations for creating data-business opportunities that will contribute to the TEF sustainability plans.

1.1. Stakeholders and Data governance requirements

In the agricultural data-sharing landscape, various stakeholders play crucial roles. Farmers, for example, are the primary data originators. The Data Act is crucial for protecting farmers' rights to access the data collected by the connected products and related services they use in their fields and farms¹. It establishes legal guidelines for data access and sharing with third parties, ensuring farmers' control over their data. This act fosters a more balanced and transparent data-sharing environment. Their data is crucial for the entire data economy in agriculture. Technology companies and data intermediaries collect, process, and disseminate agricultural data. They act as data holders, connecting farmers and data end-users like agribusinesses and policymakers. The landscape also includes traders, retailers, and service providers, each contributing to data-sharing.

Data ownership and access rights are critical considerations in the agreements governing the TEF services. Establishing clear guidelines on who owns the data and the conditions under which it can be shared or used outside its original context is critical to ensuring flexibility and maximizing opportunities for all stakeholders. Whether the data is collected by customers using their own devices or by the facility owners through additional monitoring equipment, consent management and adherence to data-sharing protocols will play a central role.

Moreover, for facility-generated data, where the primary intent is business-oriented data collection, the facility owners have full control over the data without the need for additional negotiations. However, to ensure the data collected is useful and interoperable across different applications, it is essential that all stakeholders agree on common data

¹ Osborne Clarke (Feb 7th, 2024) "What is the impact of the EU Data Act on Agritech?", <https://www.osborneclarke.com/insights/what-impact-eu-data-act-agritech>

structures, ontologies, and standards. This alignment will ensure that data can be effectively shared and reused within the TEF ecosystem.

1.2. Key building blocks of Dataspace

As highlighted in the Dataspace Support Center (DSSC) reports², building blocks are the key components of dataspace architecture. Those building blocks can be categorized into technical and business and organizational Fig. Fig. 18 . The organizational and business building blocks of dataspace ensure financial sustainability, legal compliance, and value creation, whereas the technical building blocks define capabilities and common specifications, guiding informed technical decisions and identifying open standards.

The reference architecture for dataspace developed by the International Dataspace Association (IDSA) defines a connector as a key software component that allows entities to join the dataspace and interact with other participants and services. A connector may implement a separation of concerns, meaning it may have a control plane and one or more data planes. Data planes are responsible for secure data transfer between participants. This involves data sources, ingestion, storage, processing, and analytics. In agriculture, this includes collecting data from IoT devices and sensors and then processing and analyzing it for decision-making. These components must ensure interoperability, enabling different systems to communicate effectively.

Fig. 1 – Dataspace building blocks

On the organizational side, connector's "Control Plane" covers governance, identity, access management, and data sovereignty. Trust between partners is established through identity frameworks and data sovereignty, allowing data owners, like farmers, to maintain control over their data. Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) and other identity management technologies are key elements of trust between dataspace participants and ensure secure and compliant data

² DSSC Blueprint: <https://dssc.eu/page/knowledge-base>

exchanges. Data marketplaces further facilitate data sharing by managing metadata and enforcing contracts. IDS-RAM is one of the standards that ensures secure data exchange and governance through components like dataspace connectors and clearinghouses. These components work together to maintain data sovereignty and compliance in the dataspace ecosystem.

2. Common technologies used in implementing Dataspaces

There are multiple existing initiatives relevant to the implementation of agricultural dataspaces. While existing references offer valuable knowledge and perspectives, the implementation of dataspaces in agriculture will need to evolve gradually. Creating a completely new design would create significant challenges due to integration with the existing solutions. Instead, the development of agricultural dataspaces will likely follow an evolutionary path, driven by market demands and practical requirements. The following sections will provide further guidance to ensure that agricultural dataspaces are equipped with the necessary tools to develop effective and adaptable solutions.

2.1. Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC)

Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) project³ is an initiative supported by the Eclipse Foundation, aimed at creating multi-organizational dataspaces enabling data sharing between entities with varying levels of trust. These dataspaces combine both technical infrastructure and organizational agreements to ensure secure data exchanges across different participants. EDC provides a solution to key challenges in data sharing, such as secure publication, multi-cloud sharing, and control over shared data.

EDC provides architecture, code, and examples, allowing developers to build upon its core features, which are designed for both functional and non-functional purposes. Its flexibility is ensured by APIs that support customization, aligning with Gaia-X AISBL specifications and IDSA Dataspace Protocol (DSP) for interoperability. One of EDC's standout features is the use of Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs), which eliminate the need for central authorities in verifying identities. DIDs enable entities to maintain control over their identifiers, enhancing privacy and trust. EDC uses cryptographic systems to verify claims, which further secures the identities of participants.

³ <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.edc>

Fig. 2 – EDC architecture (Source: IDSA).

The key components under development by the EDC project are:

- **Identity Service:** Manages and verifies credentials using DIDs and W3C Verifiable Credentials or OAuth2 tokens.
- **Catalog Service:** Enables discovery and sharing of data assets across different organizations.
- **Data Plane and Monitoring Services:** Initiates and manages data transfers using off-the-shelf protocols such as HTTP, Kafka, and cloud object storage. The Data Plane can be extended to support other technologies.
- **Control Plane:** Allows the automated creation and processing of data usage agreements that grant access to data.

The **Connector** shown in Fig. 4 is a pair of components that control data sharing and execute data transfer. These components are the Control Plane and Data Plane, respectively.

EDC also provides two additional services: the **Registration Service** and the **Data Dashboard**. The Registration Service was developed to manage the onboarding of new participants, ensuring they meet the dataspace's criteria. It maintains trust and integrity by enforcing compliance with policies. This component was created for the Minimum Viable Dataspace to showcase dataspace technologies, but it was not intended for production use. Accordingly, the repository for the Registration Service was archived in June 2024⁴. The Data Dashboard, also known as the Management UI, offers a user interface for managing data sharing activities, making it easier for participants to control data exchanges and track usage.

Additionally, the project offers **samples** and a **Minimum Viable Dataspace (MVD)**. These samples can be used for learning purposes, ranging from basic scenarios involving file sharing to advanced use cases such as streaming and handling large data sets. The EDC Minimum Viable Dataspace (MVD) is a demonstration dataspace between two organizations.

⁴ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/RegistrationService>

The main features presently offered by the mentioned components are:

- **Interoperability:** Ensures seamless integration and communication between different data sharing systems. EDC components are standard-based and implement the **Dataspace Protocol Specification** and **Decentralized Claims Protocol Specification**.
- **Data Sovereignty:** Maintains control over data even after it has been shared by means of usage and access policies.
- **Security:** Implements robust security measures to protect data during exchange.
- **Extensibility:** Designed to support additional protocols and custom integrations.

While the EDC framework is one of the most comprehensive options available, it has not yet been confirmed as the reference implementation for AgrifoodTEF, though its components offer a strong foundation for exploring dataspaces.

2.2. Pontus-X

Pontus-X⁵ is a decentralized digital ecosystem. It enables companies and institutions to consume, offer and monetize data, software and infrastructure services within a trusted and transparent environment. Pontus-X is built on Gaia-X principles and Ocean Enterprise⁶ technology, emphasizing decentralization and data sovereignty. It facilitates technically enforced data-sovereign data sharing and digital service monetization, all while strictly adhering to the rules of the Gaia-X Trust Framework, as detailed in Section 2.3.

It allows companies and institutions to consume and offer AI, software, data and infrastructure services in the Pontus-X ecosystem while remaining in control of their IP and sensitive data, thus meeting GDPR and IT security requirements. The Pontus-X portals provide a place to publish, discover, select, and consume digital service offerings, providing a user interface to interact with federation and other ecosystem services. Besides the portals, all services can be managed and consumed programmatically through libraries such as Nautilus⁷.

Within Pontus-X, you can utilize federated analysis, machine learning (ML) algorithms and AI (Artificial Intelligence) services to extract valuable information from data services or offer access to sensitive data without exposing it to unnecessary third-party or compliance risks. One of the core features of the Pontus-X ecosystem for Gaia-X is a data access and orchestration mechanism called Compute-to-Data (CtD), detailed in Section 2.4. CtD enables data owners to grant only computation access to their data without creating copies in other environments you do not control.

Pontus-X goes beyond the federation services by natively supporting settling business cases through EU-regulated E-money EUROe and supporting sustainable business operations for all participants providing infrastructure and services.

The Pontus-X ecosystem for Gaia-X was deployed and officially launched by deltaDAO in 2021 during the first Gaia-X Hackathon event and has been continuously developed, evolved, and grown since then. Today, Pontus-X features the

⁵ Pontus-X Open-Source Framework for the Industrial AI & Data Economy, <https://www.pontus-x.eu>

⁶ Ocean Enterprise, <https://www.oceanenterprise.io>

⁷ Nautilus, the Typescript data economy toolkit, <https://nautilus.delta-dao.com>

complete set of federation services, added ecosystem services from various providers, and is connected to the Gaia-X Digital Clearing Houses (GXDCH), the Gaia-X Compliance Service, and the Gaia-X Registry. It features hundreds of service offerings from Europe and across the Gaia-X domains while rapidly enabling the community to develop digital services for an open ecosystem.

The Pontus-X ecosystem is designed to empower all participants, allowing them to become a federation without relying on any centralized component. This unique structure ensures that no single point of failure or control exists within its stack. Participants can contribute and share the common infrastructure, and any participant or federator can cease participation at any time, without disrupting the ecosystem's function. This flexibility supports a full range of business models for all participants, ensuring the ecosystem's sustainability.

The federated ecosystem services of Pontus-X are bolstered by a wide range of applications and open-source software, particularly in the form of smart contracts. Pontus-X leverages free open-source software from the Ocean Protocol software stack to support a variety of services, including data exchange, catalogue, contracting, and orchestration of software, infrastructure, and data services. The Pontus-X ecosystem architecture is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 – Pontus-X ecosystem architecture (source: <https://docs.pontus-x.eu>)

2.3. Gaia-X

The Gaia-X architecture facilitates data infrastructure ecosystems by utilizing key components such as the Gaia-X Conceptual Model, Operational Model, Federation Services, and the Gaia-X Trust Framework. Gaia-X is composed of multiple individual ecosystems that adhere to the architecture and meet the Gaia-X standards.

The overall Gaia-X Ecosystem is essentially a virtual network of Participants, Service Offerings, and Resources that comply with the Gaia-X Trust Framework. Participants in this ecosystem can serve as both Consumers and Providers, with services typically offered via Federated Catalogues. The governance of the Gaia-X ecosystem involves Policy Rules, which define objectives, practices, and regulations that guide the activities of Participants, alongside the Trust Framework.

As shown in Fig. 4, the Gaia-X architecture addresses key aspects such as compliance, federation, and interoperable data exchange through the following components:

- Data Exchange is facilitated through a combination of Gaia-X Data Exchange services and Connectors.
- Federation enables the federation of Gaia-X-specific and ecosystem-specific services. Verifiable Credentials facilitate identity federation and can be managed by tools like the Gaia-X VC Wizard⁸. Catalogues can be also federated thanks to service offerings also modelled as Verifiable Credentials and their announcement through the Credentials Event Service⁹.
- Compliance is ensured by adhering to Gaia-X specifications, Policy Rules, Label criteria, and ecosystem-defined rules.

⁸ Gaia-X VC Wizard, <https://wizard.lab.gaia-x.eu>

⁹ Credentials Event Service, <https://gaia-x.eu/news-press/gaia-x-and-catalogues>

Fig. 4 – Gaia-X Framework

Interoperability between independent, autonomous ecosystems is enabled through three distinct planes:

- Trust Plane: This plane represents the global digital governance shared across ecosystems. It is governed by the Trust Framework and operationalized by services such as the Gaia-X Compliance and Registry services.
- Management Plane: This extends the common governance provided by ecosystem Federators, including specific contract templates for vertical markets like finance or healthcare, which may have additional regulations.
- Usage Plane: This plane focuses on technical interoperability, especially between different Service Offerings.

2.4. Compute-to-data

Compute-to-Data (CtD) is a computation approach that facilitates privacy and data sovereignty by design. Algorithms are executed where the data is stored. Data providers keep control of the data, it is not copied anywhere else, as shown in Fig. 5. Thus, instead of sharing raw data, parties send computation instructions to the data holder, who executes the instructions on the data locally and shares only the results. This approach reduces data exposure and maintains data control. The data can remain in a secure environment to minimize data leaks risk.

Fig. 5 – Conventional Data Exchange compared to Compute-to-Data (source: <https://docs.pontus-x.eu>)

One of the main limitations when implementing CtD is that it requires coordination between data owners and computation requesters, as well as secure communication and execution environments. Computation requesters need to ensure their computation tasks are compatible with the data format and structure held by the data provider. On the other hand, providers require mechanisms to verify that the computations sent to their data can be trusted or, at least,

to avoid undesirable kinds of processing like making a copy of the data. To this end, it might be helpful to use Trusted Execution Environments (TEE) or at least isolated execution environments and verify the output results before they are sent to the consumer to rule out any kind of leakage.

Application Example: Agricultural organizations can provide computation instructions for yield projections based on historical data held by farmers, sharing only the projections. The computation can be performed on the farm premises, or on thus provided by a trusted third party, like a farmers' association.

2.5. Comparisons and shortcomings

Ensuring interoperability across different technologies for dataspace implementation in the AgrifoodTEF project is crucial. As the project evolves, it will be necessary for different nodes and satellites within AgrifoodTEF to work together, making sure that the dataspace infrastructure becomes the authoritative source for data related to AI and robotics field experimentation in agriculture. This effort will require partners to adopt compliant tools that can seamlessly integrate with the broader dataspace ecosystem.

In AgriFoodTEF, we have explored the most prominent solutions for the implementation of dataspaces, including the Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC), the Gaia-X Federation Services (GXFS), and the Pontus-X (Gaia-X Web3) Ecosystem. Overall, the existing solutions have different strengths and weaknesses, and in most cases, it will depend on the target use cases which one will be more suitable.

For the first deployment of the AgrifoodTEF dataspace, Pontus-X has been selected due to various factors that differentiate it from other solutions. The most relevant ones are:

- Pontus-X provides a more ready-to-use dataspace solution with a Web Portal featuring a fully-fledged marketplace, which allows fast creation of a new dataspace or joining an existing dataspace.
- Additionally, Pontus-X supports data sovereignty by implementing an out-of-the box compute-to-data approach. This functionality solves the trade-off between the benefits of using private data and the risks of exposing it. It allows data consumers to run computer jobs on private data while the data stays on premises with the data provider.
- Moreover, Pontus-X features Gaia-X Compliance & Interoperability, enabling the verification of Gaia-X service credentials and semantic interoperability across X-ecosystems, leveraging Gaia-X Digital Clearing Houses (GXDCH) services by default.

Some of the weaknesses, though, of Pontus-X compared to EDC that we found relevant so far are regarding the data access policies, and the integration of non-standard data transfer destinations (e.g., integrating a cloud/institutional storage solution). Pontus-X includes only a few pre-defined access policies (e.g., license definition), while in EDC the policy engine allows the specification of different types of policies using the standard ODRL vocabulary. The policies are then enforced via additional modules that can be added to the connector.

The following table provides an overview of the main components for each dataspace solution, based on and updated from Gaia-X white paper Building a Dataspace: Technical Overview¹⁰:

	EDC	GXFS	Pontus-X
Repository	https://github.com/eclipse-edc	https://gitlab.com/gaia-x/data-infrastructure-federation-services	https://github.com/deltaDAO/mvg-portal
Identity & Trust	IAM modules (oath, did, daps) Identity Hub	Authentication & Authorization Services Personal Credential Manager Organizational Credential Manager	DID on Pontus-X network SSI wallet
Catalogue	Connector catalogue Federated catalogue	Federated catalogue Self-description wizard	Federated Catalogue: metadata smart contracts on-chain Cache for metadata
Exchange	Data plane with extensions for different protocols Control plane for contracts	Data Contract Services Data Exchange Logging Service	Data contracting Service: data token smart contracts Data Exchange Logging Service: audit trail on-chain Compute-to-data environment
Compliance	Trust Framework Adoption	Validation as part of authentication/authorization Continuous Automated Monitoring Service Notarization Service	Validation as part of an SSI layer Trust Framework Adoption
UI	Data Dashboard (only for demonstration)	Portal	Portal
Other	Registration service	Orchestration service	Voting service

Finally, it is also important to consider the implications of the Pontus-X approach with the compute-to-data intermediaries compared to the peer-to-peer data-sharing approach of connectors like EDC. From the Data Governance Act (DGA) perspective, the presence of these intermediaries providing the compute-to-data environments might require their registration as a Data Intermediaries following the DGA principles¹¹. Though this might add additional administrative burdens for entities offering this kind of service in the context of a Pontus-X dataspace, this registration requirement should provide additional guarantees to all stakeholders, beyond the technical guarantees of data sovereignty already provided by the compute-to-data approach to data processing.

2.6. Rationale for a Decentralized or Federated Dataspace Architecture

¹⁰ <https://www.gaia-x.at/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/WhitepaperGaiaX.pdf>

¹¹ Data Governance Act Data Intermediary Services, <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/es/policies/data-intermediary-services>

Rationale for a Decentralized or Federated Dataspace Architecture

The decision to adopt a decentralized approach rather than a centralized data architecture was primarily driven by two factors. Firstly, centralised models require centralised and dedicated infrastructure and resources, which some partners are well-equipped for but unable to provide for the needs of the whole project and the deployment of a centralised data infrastructure was not envisioned during the initial planning. Secondly, we have flexibility matters to take care of. Implementing data governance and compliance with the Data Act and ensuring sovereignty is more straightforward in a federated model. Partners maintain ownership and control of the data they have generated, along with the policies governing that data, focusing only on their customer base. AgrifoodTEF project includes many partners from various EU countries and this requires flexible control policies easier to implement by decentralised models.

Decentralised dataspace architectures allow partners to retain direct control over their data and customer relationships, enable enforcement of local governance and usage policies, minimise the need for top-down policy imposition at the European project level, thereby reducing resistance from national or company-specific governance structures. Also relevant in distributed models which provide a suitable reference for AgrifoodTEF is the use of cryptographic solutions to verify and validate claims, supporting therefore authenticity and accountability for data stored in the dataspace. When a participant wants to exchange data, they might need to present claims about their identity, permissions, or the data itself. These claims are encoded in VCs and VPs, and cryptographic signatures are used to verify their authenticity and integrity. The receiver can then use the recipient's DID and the cryptographic signatures on the VCs and VPs to verify the claims and ensure that they are indeed made by the claimed issuer, which is more scalable and appropriate for AgrifoodTEF dataspace than proposing a centralised approach for achieving the same purposes.

Decentralisation also enables a more adaptable, sustainable, secure and sovereign environment for data management and sharing (not need to rely on a central authority, reduced risks of centralized data breaches) ensuring no single point of failure, and more practical and organical scalability as new nodes/participants join, besides enabling local adaptations without needing central approval, e.g., for adding new local services.

Decentralised and federated architectures provide support for better implementations when it comes to addressing **Data Classification and Access Scenarios** needs that AgrifoodTEF dataspace will have. In particular, we identified three main scenarios that we will need to tackle in AgrifoodTEF as they impact data access and governance:

- **Pre-existing Data Assets:** Partners may already possess data collected before the start of the AgrifoodTEF project. While they may wish to monetize this data by listing it in the dataspace, they may choose not to share it within the consortium due to pre-existing ownership and sensitivity and the intrinsic, though potential, monetary value. Also, other parties that are not part of AgrifoodTEF may be involved in the control of these data, so the partner may not have the liberty of sharing the data with the Consortium.
- **Data Generated During the Project as exploitable project foreground asset:** Data collected using TEF-provided equipment during the project falls under joint intellectual property regulations,

currently being outlined in the IPR (Intellectual Property Rights) framework developed and proposed by the Polimi partner. Indeed, when data are generated by a partner using AgrifoodTEF resources in the context of a service to a company, such data should be a joint project asset, unless it is an asset that belongs to *the company* served by the partner. A benefit to AgrifoodTEF (and through it also to other companies) will be negotiated for every service involving data collection as regulated by the above-mentioned IPR for Data Regulation.

- **Restricted Experimental Data:** In some cases, partners may collect data during collaborative experiments but choose not to share it, citing business protection concerns or they may be interested only to share their data only in their country/region. This scenario introduces the need for data valorisation and potential pricing discussions which can then be handled separately by individual partners on a distributed manner, rather than having to setup a central decision point which would require an additional AgrifoodTEF legal entity.

Challenges and Risks associated with exploitation of AgrifoodTEF dataspace and decision criteria

Several challenges and risks must be addressed in this context which further justify the chosen decentralized approach:

- **Technical challenges:** though decentralised, the dataspace still requires a basic level of shared infrastructure (e.g., protocols) to work, which requires maintenance that will be handled through project resources while the project is active. Such aspects will have to be duly handed-over to ensure dataspace services can outlive project duration.
- **Data Governance:** it may prove difficult to set up governance structures, to make all contributors to the dataspace happy with them, to keep these governance structures going while the dataspace evolves after the project.
- **Convincing Partners and Customers:** Gaining consent to share or grant access to data—even metadata—in the dataspace is currently met with skepticism and may be difficult to obtain.
- **IPR Management:** There is a risk that stakeholders may hesitate to sign IPR agreements without understanding the implications for their specific use cases. This includes scenarios where background data (owned prior to the project) and foreground data (generated during the project) intersect, raising ownership and usage questions.
- **Ambiguities in Data Ownership:** The actual owner of certain datasets may not be a direct AgrifoodTEF partner, adding another layer of legal complexity. Furthermore, a Partner adding its competences to further process a dataset might acquire data-ownership rights over the transformed data and the conditions for that ownership/rights transfer must be carefully evaluated.
- **Sustainability of Data Commitments and Data Persistence:** If a partner leaves the project, questions remain regarding the ownership and management of data created during their participation.

Due to the current engagement of many of the Partners of AgrifoodTEF involved in its Data Space design (FBK, U.Lleida, PSNC, ILVO, JR) involved also in the CEADS project, expected to implement the Common European Agricultural Data Space, all the above-mentioned design aspects are also aligned with the current architectural approach being studied for the European level. This will ensure that the AgrifoodTEF data space will be easily integrated into the CEADS as these projects will be running in parallel until the end of the AgrifoodTEF execution. It is also expected that some of the answers to the above-mentioned questions about the bare minimum maintenance needs for a data space infrastructure for experimental data services in Agrifood will be taken care of the upcoming EDIC Agrifood initiative that the EU has issued a tender for as part of the Digital Europe Program.

Next steps for Y3 Data Space deployment

To address these concerns and populate the AgrifoodTEF data space for Y3 execution, the following actions are being discussed:

- Encourage partners to list metadata entries in the dataspace rather than sharing full datasets. This is aligned with the decentralised data spaces paradigm, which is based on keeping the data on its original source, avoiding the centralisation of data. Metadata should include: the nature and description of the dataset, legal data-ownership and control rights, data intermediaries rights and access policies (e.g., permissions for copying, storage, or compute-to-data)
- Agree on common APIs leveraging existing standards as much as possible taking into account existing recommendations and best practices (e.g., DSSC) as well as previous results and ongoing initiatives (e.g., CEADS, AgriDataSpace) to facilitate controlled access and interoperability based on metadata catalogs. The data space will orchestrate access to these APIs and enforce the terms defined by the API and data provider.
- Revisit and strengthen the IPR framework to ensure it adequately covers all scenarios related to the dataspace, including disengagement of partners.
- Continue discussions to ensure all stakeholders understand the distinctions between centralized and federated models and the long-term implications for data ownership, monetization, and legal compliance.

3. AgriFoodTEF Dataspace Implementation

The current version of the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace is based on the Pontus-X ecosystem and some of the Gaia-X Trust Framework services as previously introduced. The following subsections detail how the dataspace can be used.

3.1. Dataspace onboarding

The initial offering for all dataspace participants, including AgrifoodTEF partners and organizations participating through AgrifoodTEF services, will be based on a managed approach. Following this approach, the AgrifoodTEF partners responsible for the data space management (FBK, PSNC or UdL) will generate private keys for the participants, provide

them to the corresponding participant, and keep them in custody for any emergency, like losing them or providing assistance by interacting with the dataspace on their behalf.

Alternatively, from the beginning or once the participant is familiarized with the AgrifoodTEF dataspace, the participants can opt for a full sovereign approach, in which they generate their own private key as instructed in the Pontus-X ecosystem documentation. It is important to note that in this case the participants will be fully responsible for their private key. This includes making sure it is not lost or leaked, keeping secure backup copies, and taking full responsibility for their interactions with the dataspace as only they will be able to do so, and no other party will be able to do so on their behalf.

To complete the onboarding step, and as required by the Pontus-X ecosystem, all participants should provide the following details about the corresponding organization. This is just information about the corresponding legal entity information, in no case will personal data be collected or registered into the Pontus-X ecosystem.

Required legal entity information for onboarding, aligned with the requirements set by the Gaia-X Trust Framework for participants description¹²:

- **Name:** short name.
- **URL:** legal entity main web address.
- **Legal name:** as officially registered.
- **Legal registration number:** for EU participants the VAT number is recommended, which can be checked online¹³. Other alternatives are EUID, EORI or LEI¹⁴.
- **Country subdivision code:** based on the ISO 3166-2¹⁵ standard, which combined the country code and a subdivision code varying in each country.
- **Legal address:** street address, postal code and locality.

Example:

- **Name:** UdL
- **URL:** <https://www.udl.cat>
- **Legal name:** Universitat de Lleida
- **VAT:** ESQ7550001G
- **Country subdivision code:** ES-L
- **Legal address:**
 - Street address: Victor Siurana, 1
 - Postal code: 25003
 - Locality: Lleida

¹² Gaia-X Trust Framework Participant, <https://gaia-x.gitlab.io/policy-rules-committee/trust-framework/participant/>

¹³ VIES VAT number validation, https://ec.europa.eu/taxation_customs/vies/#/vat-validation

¹⁴ Gaia-X Participant Legal Registration Number, <https://gaia-x.gitlab.io/policy-rules-committee/trust-framework/participant/#registrationnumber>

¹⁵ ISO 3166-2, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-2

The AgrifoodTEF partners responsible for dataspace management will register this information through the established channels in the Pontus-X ecosystem. This step is required to operate in the ecosystem. Additionally, the dataspace management partners will offer the participants the option of generating and storing their Participant Verifiable Credentials based on the previous legal entity information and compatible with the Gaia-X Trust Framework. Alternatively, detailed instructions¹⁶ and sample source¹⁷ code will be provided to participants so they can generate, digitally sign and store their own credentials in a self-sovereign way.

Examples of credentials for some of the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace participants:

- Universitat de Lleida's Verifiable Presentation of its credentials, which include the Legal Participant credential, the Legal Registration Number credential and the Gaia-X Terms and Conditions credential: <https://compliance.agrospai.udl.cat/.well-known/UdL.vp.json>

The previous credentials can be validated using the Gaia-X Digital Clearing House (GXDCH) service, for instance the staging variant of version 1 of GCDCH: <https://compliance.lab.gaia-x.eu/v1-staging/docs>

3.2. Digital Wallet Setup

Regarding the use of the private key for the interaction with the dataspace, both if the key is autonomously generated by the participant or provided by the dataspace manager, it requires the setup of a digital wallet. The recommended approach for wallet setup is to use the browser extension MetaMask, as detailed in <https://docs.pontus-x.eu/docs/getting-started/wallet-setup>. This extension is available for iOS, Android and different desktop computer browsers, as shown in Fig. 6.

¹⁶ <https://wizard.lab.gaia-x.eu/userGuide>

¹⁷ Gaia-X Compliance support scripts, https://github.com/AgrospAI/pontus-x_cli/tree/main/src/gaia-x_compliance

Fig. 6 – MetaMask download page (source: <https://metamask.io/download/>)

Once the MetaMask extension has been installed and configured with the provided private key, or one autonomously generated, the participant will be able to interact with the dataspace beyond just exploring the catalogue. This includes consuming existing datasets and services or making new datasets and services available through the dataspace, as detailed in the following subsections.

3.3. Exploring the Dataspace Marketplace

The easiest way to discover services published in the dataspace is through the main portal at dataspace.agrifoodtef.eu, or other associated portals to the same federated ecosystem, like dataspaces.psnc.pl or agrosapai.udl.cat.

The portals' landing pages offer an overview of selected data and service offerings through a catalogue that also allows filtering them, as shown in Fig. 7.

The screenshot displays the AgrifoodTEF Marketplace interface. On the left, there is a sidebar with filters for Service Type (datasets, algorithms, saas), Access Type (download, compute), and Sort Type (Relevance, Published, Sales, Price) with ascending and descending options. The main area shows a grid of asset cards. Each card includes a title, a short description, a price, and a '1 sale' indicator. Assets are categorized by tags like 'DOWNLOAD', 'COMPUTE', 'DATASET', and 'ALGORITHM'. The interface also features a top navigation bar with 'CATALOGUE', 'PUBLISH', 'VERIFY', 'LOG', and 'ECOSYSTEM' options, along with search and user profile elements.

Fig. 7 – AgrifoodTEF Marketplace (source: <https://dataspace.agrifoodtef.eu>)

The metadata summary for all listed assets informs about their name, title, short description, price, number of consumptions/sales and the network where it is registered. Additionally, each asset is tagged as “DOWNLOAD” if it can be downloaded or “COMPUTE” if it cannot and can be just consumed in a compute-to-data environment, thus guaranteeing sovereignty over its content by the asset owner. Moreover, assets can be a data asset marked as “DATASET”, or a data processing service marked as “ALGORITHM”.

There are datasets and algorithms that can be consumed by downloading the contained data or code respectively, when they are tagged “DOWNLOAD”. On the other hand, if a dataset is tagged “COMPUTE”, the data cannot be downloaded, and it can be just consumed using the compute-to-data approach. In this case, the consumer has no access to the data, it is loaded into the compute environment together with the algorithm chosen to process it, among those previously consented by the owner. The consumer has access just to the result of the computation, not to the raw data which remains in control of its owner.

When a particular asset is clicked, it is possible to inspect it in detail and more information becomes available. All assets are identified by a unique identifier, the DID. Additional information, as shown in Fig. 8, include the owner of the asset, identified by the public address corresponding to the private one associated to the corresponding participant, as previously detailed for the onboarding procedure in Section 3.1. The registered participant name is displayed instead of

its public address to improve the usability of the marketplace. Below the owner information, the token that governs access to the asset is shown.

Moreover, if a Gaia-X compliant service credential has been added to the service and if it matches this asset DID, a badge is show after validating it against a Gaia-X Digital Clearing House (GXDCH).

On the righthand side, there is a summary of the costs of consumption for this asset, denominated in a currency specified by the service provider, i.e. in EUROe. This currency will be used for pre-paid settlement for a subscription and the settlement must be completed before the asset can be accessed during the subscription period.

Exploratory Data Analysis

Pontus-X Devnet

The screenshot displays the marketplace interface for an Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) asset. On the left, the asset is titled "Owned by Universitat de ..." and "Accessed with UDL-EDA". It includes a "DOWNLOAD" button and "ALGORITHM" details. The asset was published 5 months ago by Universitat de Lleida (UdL) and updated 2 months ago. It features a "Service Credential" and "Credential ID match" badge, with version 22.10 and a last check less than a minute ago. The description states: "Generate an Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) report for the input tabular data. The input data is loaded using pandas and then the EDA report is generated using pandas-profiling. The HTML version of the report can be downloaded when the algorithm finishes. The report includes the following information: Data Quality Alerts Overview".

On the right, the pricing section shows "0,1 EUROe" and a "DOWNLOAD" button. A message states: "You bought this algorithm already allowing you to use it without paying again." Below this is a checkbox for "I agree to the Terms and Conditions" and a green confirmation message: "You successfully bought this algorithm and are now able to download it." A section titled "Datasets algorithm is allowed to run on" lists several datasets, all related to "CEP - Automatic Pig Feeding - 2021 S1", with varying DIDs and prices (0,5 and 1,5 EUROe).

Fig. 8 – Details about an asset in the marketplace (source: <https://dataspace.agrifoodtef.eu>)

3.4. Acquire an Asset

To consume a selected dataset the consumer needs first to meet the following conditions:

- It must be eligible to consume the asset or combination of assets (e.g. a dataset and the algorithm to process if consumption is limited to compute). By default, the services can be consumed by any participant unless the owner restricts access to certain potential consumers or purposes.
- The consumer must have a sufficient balance associated to its public address, enough to cover network fees and cover the costs for all the involved assets, plus the compute resources to execute the algorithm over the dataset if the consumption is restricted to the compute-to-data approach.

- The consumer must be connected through the portal to the network where the asset is registered and do so using its public address.

If all conditions are met the buy button will indicate this by being available and not greyed out. If not, the user receives an indication in the frontend with a message describing the issue and information about how to solve it.

If the consumption is triggered, the user will be then asked to sign several transactions. If the type of asset consumption is by download, the procedure is as follows:

- Register the consent with the Terms and Conditions of the asset.
- Make the required balance available for the transaction.
- Pay for the asset to acquire the token granting access to it.
- Finally, exchange the acquired access token to consume the asset, in this case by download.

The first transaction will set and approve a maximum spending cap for the following transaction that determines how much is allowed to be paid for the service. In the next step the consumer approves a second transaction to exchange currency against the access token required for the asset. This transaction will include the network fees to cover the cost of federation services and infrastructure provided by federators (network validators). When approved, the transaction will be submitted to the network, the exchange will be facilitated and the acquired access token will be exchanged to execute the right to use the service. This creates an audit trail entry and marks the beginning of the service subscription which is documented in the federated logging service.

The access controller used by the service provider will use this audit trail event and proof of transaction to determine if a user has the right to access the service and to check the identity of a user. All participants will be able to assess the status of the transaction through the logging service, as detailed in 3.9.

Now the service can be downloaded as detailed in the next subsection. Please note that in the case of an asset restricted to compute consumption, there will be a second service offering and contracting process involved and at least 5 transactions are required as two contracts with up to three parties will be stipulated (the data owner, the algorithm provider and the party contributing the compute-to-data resources). After registering these transactions, and once the compute-to-data process has completed the execution of the algorithm on the dataset, the results of the computation will be available for consumption as detailed in the next subsection.

3.5. Consuming an Acquired Asset

Now that the asset has been acquired, it can be consumed. If the consumption type is “download”, it will be signaled by the availability of an activated “Download” button. When the consumption is requested, the dataspace access controller designated by the asset provider will check that the identity of the consumer matches the identity of the party who acquired the asset. For this reason, a signature request is performed to prove the consumer has control of the private key associated with the public address of the consumer. If the signature has been verified successfully by the access controller, the file can be downloaded. Similarly, if the consumption is based on compute-to-data, the results of the computation can just be downloaded after verifying the consumer identity.

It is also possible to access your consumption history via the dataspace marketplace, going through the “View Profile” option associated with the current user, as shown in Fig. 9. Once the identify has been connected through the MetaMask extension, or a similar one that allows managing the associated private key. Under the section “Downloads”, the current user will find a full overview of all services that have been acquired for downloading. And under the section “Compute Jobs”, there is a summary for all “compute” processes triggered by the user, the respective audit trails and the options to access the results of previous computations.

DATASET	NETWORK	PROVIDER	CREATED	FINISHED	STATUS	ACTIONS
Pig pen images se...	Pontus-X Devnet	https://provider.angliru...	8 days ago	8 days ago	JOB FINISHED	SHOW DETAILS
Red Wine Dataset	Pontus-X Testnet	https://provider.agrosp...	17 days ago	17 days ago	JOB FINISHED	SHOW DETAILS
Red Wine Dataset	Pontus-X Testnet	https://provider.agrosp...	about 1 month ago	about 1 month ago	JOB FINISHED	SHOW DETAILS

Fig. 9 – User profile with history of acquired assets for download and compute-to-data (source: <https://dataspace.agrifoodtef.eu>)

3.6. Publishing a Dataset

Adding a dataset to the dataspace means registering its metadata so it is listed in the marketplace so it can be acquired and consumed. Just the metadata is recorded in the dataspace infrastructure, the data remains under the control of the data holder. Publication can be performed interactively from the dataspace marketplace by selection the top menu option “Publish”, as shown in Fig. 10. The publishing form collects first the required metadata for the dataset, including

title, description, tags... Then, the publisher also needs to provide how the dataset is made accessible, through “download” or “compute”.

In both cases a “Data Provider” will intermediate to enforce access rules. The default provider can be used, though the publisher has the freedom to define a custom one. Additional information for access includes where the data is available from (usually the URL from where it can be downloaded and that will be kept private by the “Data Provider”), the timeout for consumption or a link to a sample file that helps potential consumers get an idea about the data. The next step in the form is about setting dataset pricing, which might be offered for free or for a price in EUROe, a test version of a digital currency tied to the Euro. This is the recommended currency to make pricing more transparent for consumers.

Finally, it is possible to review how the asset will be presented in the marketplace before confirming publication by signing the corresponding transactions that will keep immutable record of the publication and tie the dataset to the account signing the transactions.

Publish into Pontus-X Devnet [ⓘ]

Highlight the important features of your dataset or algorithm to make it more discoverable and catch the interest of data consumers.

1 Metadata — 2 Access — 3 Pricing — 4 Preview — 5 Submit

Data NFT* [ⓘ]

GX Data NFT — GX-NFT
This NFT represents an asset in Ocean Protocol v4 ecosystems.

Asset Type*

Dataset > Algorithm

Title*

e.g. Shapes of Desert Plants

Description* [ⓘ]

Service Credential [ⓘ]

e.g. <https://file.com/service-credential.json> VALIDATE

Fig. 10 – Dataset publishing form (source: <https://dataspace.agrifoodtef.eu>)

Alternatively, it is also possible to publish a dataset from code using the Nautilus¹⁸ Typescript library or from the command line using the “publish” command of the Pontus-X CLI¹⁹.

3.7. Publishing an Algorithm

The AgrifoodTEF Dataspace supports publishing both datasets and algorithms. The later are data processing services that are packaged as Docker containers and scripts to be run on the context of those containers. Publication is triggered interactively the same way datasets are published, through the “Publish” menu bar option. In the associated form, it is necessary to select “Algorithm” as the asset type instead of “Dataset”.

Moreover, in addition to metadata like title, description or tags, it is also necessary to define the Docker image to use for the algorithm. Regarding access details, a pointer should be provided to the location of the script triggering the execution of the algorithm in the context of the container. More details about how to package and algorithm to be executed in the dataspace are provided in Ocean Protocol’s “Writing Algorithms”²⁰. Additionally, there are examples at the ocean-algo²¹ repository.

Algorithms can be made available for “Download” or just for “Compute”. In the first case the script used by the algorithm will be available for download after it is acquired. In both cases, the algorithm can be consumed together with a dataset that is configured for compute-to-data consumption. Like for datasets, it is also possible to define the deadline for consumption after acquisition or the algorithm price. Finally, after reviewing algorithm’s metadata, publication is confirmed by signing the corresponding transactions.

Alternatively, it is also possible to publish a dataset from code using the Nautilus²² Typescript library or from the command line using the “publish” command of the Pontus-X CLI²³.

3.8. Access and usage policies

The AgrifoodTEF dataspace implements the set of access and usage policies implemented in the Pontus-X ecosystem through smart contracts and Distributed Ledger Technology. These policies can be defined through marketplace user interface during asset publishing. Moreover, they can be configured programmatically using Nautilus or Pontus-X CLI.

For instance, as shown in Fig. 11, it is possible to define the timeout that anyone acquiring and asset (dataset or algorithm) has before it needs to be acquired again. It ranges from 1 day to 1 year. Additionally, consumption right might not expire and can be forever after acquisition.

¹⁸ Nautilus typescript library, <https://nautilus.delta-dao.com>

¹⁹ Pontus-X CLI publish command: https://github.com/AgrospAI/pontus-x_cli/blob/main/README.md#publish-options-script-folder

²⁰ Writing Algorithms: <https://docs.oceanprotocol.com/developers/compute-to-data/compute-to-data-algorithms>

²¹ Ocean Protocol Algorithms examples (in different repository branches), <https://github.com/AgrospAI/ocean-algo>

²² Nautilus typescript library, <https://nautilus.delta-dao.com>

²³ Pontus-X CLI publish command: https://github.com/AgrospAI/pontus-x_cli?tab=readme-ov-file#publish-options-script-folder

Fig. 11 – Defining asset consumption timeout during publishing (source: <https://dataspace.agrifoodtef.eu>)

Additional policy definitions instruments during asset publishing are the allow and deny lists of accounts, as shown in Fig. 12. The allow list defines which dataspace participants are explicitly allowed to consume the asset (dataset or algorithm). If the list is empty anyone can download or compute this asset. On the other hand, if an address is in the deny list, download or compute of this asset will be denied for the corresponding data set participant.

Fig. 12 – Defining allowed and denied accounts for asset consumption during publishing (source: <https://dataspace.agrifoodtef.eu>)

Finally, it is also possible to edit an existing dataset configured for “compute” consumption to define the individual algorithms that are allowed to run over the dataset, as shown in Fig. 13. Additionally, allowed algorithms for a dataset can be also customized by the dataset owner using the “edit-trusted-algos” in Pontus-X CLI²⁴.

²⁴ Pontus-X CLI edit-trusted-algos command: https://github.com/AgrospAI/pontus-x_cli/blob/main/README.md#edit-trusted-algos-did-algos

EDIT METADATA
EDIT COMPUTE SETTINGS

Set allowed algorithms

Only the algorithms selected here will be allowed to run on your dataset. Uncheck all to remove any access to your dataset.

Selected Algorithms ⓘ

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Exploratory Data Analysis ↗ <small>UDL-EDA did:op:34d5f73d77550843201ee1a43ad9d404d3e557ed6a70772e9afde7a27d863b8f0,1</small>
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CEP's CSV Data Mapper and Semantic Data Pooler ↗ <small>CEP-MP did:op:d20f956e79709fb2469fffe2bd85cf2fec95a21d2497998bb530043c6bbec901Free</small>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Image Recognition and Tracking for Animal Well-being Monitoring ↗ <small>CVC-SEG-TRK did:op:2c0e29e89bee015cbbbaa46ce7f9a566a2cb541367bca926c5552a1b2d6978921</small>

All Algorithms ⓘ

Allow any published algorithm

Fig. 13 – Defining allowed algorithms for a dataset set for compute consumption (source: <https://dataspace.agrifoodtef.eu>)

3.9. Data provenance and traceability

All transactions, during publication or acquisition are registered using Distributed Ledger. Technologies so an immutable record of the mis kept. All the transactions can also be seen in the Logging Explorer for the used network, as shown in Fig. 14 for the Pontus-X development network Devnet.

Using this ledger, it is possible to link all assets to the participants who published them, limit to that participant who can edit or revoke the asset, track all acquisitions of the assets and verify that just a participant who has acquired an asset can consume it. Consequently, through the Logging Explorer, it is possible to audit the AgrifoodTEF dataspace.

Fig. 14 – Pontus-X federated logging service (source: <https://explorer.pontus-x.eu/pontusx/dev>)

3.10. Data models and formats

The Data Models and Formats building block describes the capabilities to define and use shared semantics in a dataspace. It establishes a common format for data model specifications and serialization of data in data exchange payloads. Combined with the Data Exchange APIs building block, this ensures full interoperability among participants.

Data models are the common languages to facilitate semantic interoperability in a dataspace, including vocabularies, ontologies, application profiles, schema specifications, mappings and API specifications that can be used to annotate and describe data sets and data services.

As described in the DSSC Building Blocks documentation, data models are typically domain specific, and dataspace should try as much as possible to reuse existing resources, preferable standards or standard-based. So, instead of creating custom and isolated models, it is recommended to leverage existing standards, whenever possible, particularly in the form of ontologies or other semantic artifacts, which provide application-independent specification of a domain or area of interest, and which can be easily extended/adapted to specific needs.

The challenge is to agree on the model to be used. In the agriculture domain, in particular, there are dozens of ontologies/vocabularies, which have been created for different purposes/applications. Currently over 150 resources are

available just in Agroportal²⁵, the largest repository of ontologies, vocabularies and other semantic resources related to agriculture, generally each having a different focus or specialization. So, instead of requiring agreeing on only one model, more recent approaches focus on creating the interoperability pathways between existing standards and well-known models.

To maximize the interoperability with different systems and existing data, an important feature recommended for such a model is to include such alignments or pathways. This is the case, for example, of the Agriculture Information Model²⁶ (AIM). AIM is an OGC candidate standard that harmonizes and aligns relevant cross-domain standard ontologies and data models (e.g., W3C Time Ontology, OGC/W3C SOSA/SSN, OGC GeoSparql, QUDT, W3C Data Cubes, ISO geographic technology standards) with agri-specific models such as Saref4Agri, agri SmartDataModel/FIWARE and INSPIRE/FOODIE, bridging various views on the agriculture data and providing a formal representation that enables unambiguous translations between them and the basis for a semantic interoperability dataspace. AIM also provides a metadata layer that is based on DCAT (plus extensions) and IDS information model.

The AgrifoodTEF Dataspace does not make the use of data models and ontologies like AIM a pre-requisite for participants to contribute their datasets. This might become an entry barrier too big for dataspace bootstrapping so, following the Pay-as-you-go approach²⁷, participants are allowed to share their data using any format and data model. To facilitate interoperability, the dataspace integrates algorithms focusing on mapping data formats to vocabularies and ontologies like AIM. There is an example of this mechanism of semantic integration as needed in the use case presented in Section 4.1.

3.11. Dataspace governance

The Pontus-X ecosystem also provides a building block for dataspace governance. It is a voting tool²⁸ that make it possible to create polls. To participate in a poll or create one, the participant must connect its wallet with one of the accounts previously registered during the onboarding process detailed in Section 3.1. This ensures secure and verified interaction with the polling system.

The voting tool, displayed in Fig. 15, allows defining questions with multiple responses, restricting voting to participants with certain digital credentials based on DLT tokens or balance voting power based on the amounts of these tokens. Finally, once the deadline for voting has been reached, the poll can be configured to just publish the percentages for each answer, also display who has voted but not what they have voted or show the individual votes for each answer.

²⁵ Agroportal repository of ontologies and semantic artefacts in agri-food and related domains, <https://agroportal.lirmm.fr>

²⁶ Agriculture Information Model (AIM), <https://w3id.org/demeter/agri>

²⁷ Pay-as-you-go approach to data management, <https://dataspaces.info/pay-as-you-go-services>

²⁸ Pontus-X voting tool, <https://vote.pontus-x.eu>

Shall Operating Company Y be removed for poor service quality?

Please decide if Operating Company Y (Gaia-X Credential) shall be removed from the ecosystem and the provisioning of base services due to the repeated failure to provide quality of service for ecosystem base services?

Share poll on

Fig. 15 – Pontus-X voting tool for dataspace governance (source: <https://vote.pontus-x.eu>)

4. AgrifoodTEF use cases and Datasets

4.1. UdL and CEP Use Case in the Pig Sector

The aim of this use case in the pig sector is to explore the opportunities of data-sharing offered by dataspace, especially regarding how data sharing barriers might be reduced by guaranteeing that data originators remain in control of their data. Thus, the dataspace implementation is based on the Gaia-X Pontus-X ecosystem, utilizing a Web3 and blockchain-based infrastructure that provides Data Sovereignty by Design. Moreover, as Pontus-X is based on Gaia-X, its building blocks are used to facilitate dataspace federation, especially the Gaia-X Digital Clearing House (GXDCH)²⁹. Concretely:

- All participants are identified using self-descriptions validated by the GXDCH Compliance³⁰ service, which is based on the trust framework provided by the GXDCH Registry³¹. Moreover, the GXDCH Notary³² service is used

²⁹ <https://compliance.lab.gaia-x.eu>

³⁰ <https://compliance.lab.gaia-x.eu/development/docs>

³¹ <https://registry.lab.gaia-x.eu/development/docs>

³² <https://registrationnumber.notary.lab.gaia-x.eu/development/docs>

to generate a Verifiable Claim with the legal registration number for all participants. The compliant self-descriptions for the participants are:

- Universitat de Lleida (UdL):
<https://compliance.agrospai.udl.cat/.well-known/UdL.vp.json>
- Centre of Swine Studies of Catalonia (CEP):
<https://compliance.agrospai.udl.cat/.well-known/CEP.vp.json>
- Dataset and services made available through the dataspace also feature self-descriptions, which are also validated by GXDCH Compliance, for instance:
 - Exploratory Data Analysis service:
<https://agrospai.udl.cat/asset/did:op:34d5f73d77550843201ee1a43ad9d404d3e557ed6a70772e9afde7a27d863b8f>
- Dataset and services self-descriptions, after compliance has been checked, are announced through the GXDCH Credentials Event Service³³ (CES) so they can be included in federated catalogues. For instance: <https://ces-development.lab.gaia-x.eu/credentials-events/0b041d31-e306-4a54-96d1-a4f9ef818877>

The use case is run by Universitat de Lleida (UdL) in cooperation with the Centre of Swine Studies of Catalonia (CEP), an experimental pig farm managed by a consortium made up of the Diputació de Lleida, the Regional Council of La Noguera, the Torrelameu Town Hall and the Universitat de Lleida. CEP's role is mainly as data originator, willing to share through the dataspace the data generated as a result of the different experiments conducted in the pig farm. For CEP, it is crucial that they can remain in control of the data they contribute, especially when it is generated by third parties like automatic feed machine manufacturers testing their products at CEP.s at CEP.

Additionally, the monetization mechanisms provided by the Pontus-X system are being tested to evaluate different incentive mechanisms that make the use case sustainable beyond the current proof of concept phase.

Currently, two services are being offered, based on data provided by CEP. First, based on images from video surveillance of one of the CEP pens, an animal well-being assessment algorithm performs automatic image segmentation and tracking to identify and track pig movements. Additionally, it is also possible to monitor the visits of pigs to defined areas of interest like the automatic feeding machine or the waterer bowl. This allows for the automatic generation of metrics that can be used for animal well-being assessment.

Data sovereignty is guaranteed by design through a Data Room implemented using "Compute-to-Data", as shown in Fig. 16 . The algorithm visits the image sequence inside the data room, where they are analyzed, and just the computed metrics leave the room. Consequently, there is no leakage of any image from inside the farm. They are just copied to the data room and destroyed after the computation without leaving it. A sample dataset, which has CEP's consent to be "visited" by the well-being assessment algorithm, is available online³⁴.

³³ <https://ces-development.lab.gaia-x.eu/q/swagger-ui/>

³⁴ <https://dataspace.angliru.udl.cat/asset/did:op:31d6d1ea0fc540e1ea6e5268ebfd53e8129992cd6971dfbbbd0b88b08ca6f939>

Fig. 16 – Sovereign data sharing of CEP’s data through a Data Room based on “Compute-to-Data”

The second service supports the "Pay-as-you-go" approach when sharing data through a dataspace. Instead of requiring that publishers integrate the data based on existing schemas, which causes a significant upfront overhead, the pay-as-you-go paradigm favours an incremental approach. This way, entry barriers are lowered, and it becomes easier to share data.

Data is published in tabular form, for instance that generated by CEP’s automatic feeding machines. Semantic integration is provided by an algorithm implementing RML, an extension of the R2RML W3C standard, which in addition to mapping from relational databases to RDF semantic data, also provides mappings from CSV, TSV, XML and JSON data sources to RDF.

Moreover, data sovereignty is guaranteed by design through the Data Room. The mapped data does not leave the room, it is processed and then stored into a Knowledge Graph that stays inside the room. This way, it remains under the control of the data originator, the Centre of Swine Studies of Catalonia (CEP).

Later, CEP can decide to grant access to trusted algorithms to visit the Data Room and slice the Knowledge Graph to extract the semantically integrated data relevant to their computations. Also in this case, data sovereignty is guaranteed as just computation results, like aggregations or AI-trained models, can leave the room, not the original data or subsets of it.

Currently, CEP can directly share their existing tabular data about Daily Pig-Weight and Automatic Feeding Machine Data. This data remains under their control, as CEP can decide which algorithms can visit it in the Data Room. For instance, and Exploratory Data Analysis algorithm to build summaries of the data³⁵.

³⁵ <https://dataspace.angliru.udl.cat/asset/did:op:34d5f73d77550843201ee1a43ad9d404d3e557ed6a70772e9afde7a27d863b8f>

Additionally, the RML Mapper algorithm³⁶ provides mappings for CEP’s Daily Weight and Automatic Feeding Machine data formats that makes it possible to follow the incremental and tiered approach proposed by the pay-as-you-go paradigm. It maps these kinds of CSV data to W3C RDF semantic data based on well-established vocabularies and ontologies that facilitate data integration, even across use cases and activity sectors.

The mapping implemented by this algorithm generates RDF data based on the Smart Applications REference (SAREF) ontology, a vocabulary supported by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) that facilitates data integration in the smart applications domain.

For instance, for the Daily Pig Weight data:

Animal ID	Date	Weight (g)
982091062894196	2021-03-16	16300

And the Automatic Feeding Machine data:

Pen Number	Animal ID	Date	Time	Duration (s)	Feed (g)	Animal Weight (g)
4	982091062894196	2021-03-17	10:46	50	14	16500

The RML mapping generates the RDF semantic data graph that integrates both data sources, as shown in Fig. 17.

³⁶ <https://dataspace.angliru.udl.cat/asset/did:op:d20f956e79709fb2469ffe2bd85cf2fec95a21d2497998bb530043c6bbec901>

Fig. 17– Semantic integration of CEP’s Daily Pig Weight and Automatic Feeding Machine data

4.2. FBK

Part of FBK’s AgrifoodTEF facilities include real fields that have been infrastructured to support advanced experimentation of digital solutions. One of these field experimentations is particularly focused on the management of water as a natural resource.

In particular, IRRITRE is a project being developed by FBK³⁷, aimed at optimizing irrigation in the Trentino region. To achieve this, multiple sensing devices are deployed in the fields. These devices primarily serve to monitor soil moisture levels and enable optimal irrigation control. However, within the project developed platform, other features able to support farming operations and management are explored and integrated. In this context, Open-source satellite data (Sentinel-2) is used to provide insights into crop health, vegetation indices, and land surface conditions, further enhancing decision-making and resource management. However, in the context of the Trentino region, characterized by small farm holdings, the challenge is to work with distributions of data over small sized fields is the limited amount of data points available per unit of analyses.

This use-case includes the generation of meaningful visualizations and KPIs to support monitoring of different crop plots through the usage of Vegetation Indices (VI) based statistics. Such features provide valuable insights into the health and vigor of crops by indicating areas of stress, disease, or nutrient/water deficiency. With Sentinel-2 provided temporal resolution, active and constant crop surveillance can take place, and farmers can identify areas of potential problems.

Dataset

Sentinel-2 data over the Area-of-Interest (AOI) was obtained, triggering an action to retrieve images and add them to the dataset. Under the same pipeline, 25 different VIs are calculated using 7 different available multispectral bands to generate 7 visualizations and KPIs for effective field and crop tracking. These KPIs are 1) VI visualization, 2) Field temporal comparison, 3) Histograms of VIs distribution, 4) Vigor over time, 5) Vigor uniformity, 6) Vigor changes and Satellite-based Crop Evapotranspiration (Etc.).

The analyses 1-6 are done based on spatial aggregations per unit of analyses: field, subsector or sector. For illustrative purposes two fields were selected (shown in Fig. 18) to support the proposed features. They were chosen due to the significant size (above average) they contain for clarity reasons.

Fig. 18 - Sample fields

³⁷ <https://portal.pontus-x.eu/profile/0x43d3004D0232243cC4878419b6897f5f50713eAE>

VI visualization is a simple crop for the spatial unit of interest and the display of the selected VI. Colour scale is by default based on min-max of data, but users can adapt for further exploration. Fig. 19 shows examples for the two selected fields.

Fig. 19 – Sample of VI

Field comparison is a visualization tool to plot side by side different temporal windows of a field or even two different fields. Such tool supports the comparison of vigour of two different areas and comparing performance. Additionally, if two temporal windows of the same area are selected, it allows to check the crop progress. Colour scale is by default based on min-max of joint distribution of data. Fig. 20 shows field comparison for the two example fields.

Fig. 20 – Sample of field comparison

Satellite-based ETC is estimated by multiplying the reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) obtained from data collected at nearby weather stations by a site-specific crop coefficient that is obtained from vegetation indices that can be monitored at high temporal and spatial resolution through sentinel-2 imagery.

Sentinel data is available with a decent temporal resolution, but not in a daily basis. Therefore, the values were interpolated daily, so that we can estimate daily values. Fig. 21 shows on the top row the daily ETC in mm, for 3 dates of 2023. As a next step it is important to distinguish between crop and non-crop pixels by masking the fields. The output from it is shown in the second row of the figure through other three daily ETC examples.

Satellite data is further enriched and enhanced with IoT measurements (soil and air temperature and humidity) and weather forecast data focused on the monitored region supporting the development of dedicated models and decision support systems that help farmers in their irrigation decisions and monitor the outcome of different strategies when it comes to assessing yield and quality of grapes.

Fig. 21 - Vineyard evapotranspiration maps (ETc)

These are just examples of datasets in the geographic and time dimension for a specific region particularly devoted to the production of quality wine. They have been produced as part of a project that brings together different actors all interested in exploring the valorisation opportunities for such a valuable asset that can then be used to feed different types of AI algorithms created by different providers for assisting winegrowers with different purposes.

4.3. PSNC

PSNC is currently implementing two different approaches for dataspace, which are being tested via different use cases and datasets. The first one is about creating an agriculture dataspace in Poland based on Pontus-X and the second one is about demonstrating a green deal dataspace based on EDC. Here, we focus on the first dataspace use case with datasets.

4.3.1 Polish agriculture dataspace use cases

The use case for creating a unified agricultural dataspace in Poland centers on transforming scattered and inconsistent agricultural datasets into a cohesive, accessible, and valuable resource. Currently, Poland's open agricultural datasets vary significantly in quality and precision, lack standardized formats, and are challenging to discover, which limits their utility. Consequently, farmers and stakeholders underutilize these datasets, often using them only in isolated or individual contexts without broader integration.

The primary goal is to establish a unified agricultural dataspace by harmonizing these datasets with consistent information models, making them accessible in a structured and standardized manner. By implementing the Agriculture

Information Model (AIM) from the Demeter project, the transformation process will unify datasets across systems, integrating metadata and agricultural vocabularies into one cohesive structure. This standardization will support data discovery, usability, and, ultimately, data-driven decision-making in agriculture. To make this dataspace easily accessible, datasets will be published with searchable metadata, allowing stakeholders to locate relevant information quickly. The system will facilitate harmonized access to data from various sources, ensuring users can find and use data seamlessly without needing specialized integrations. This harmonization is essential for preparing data from disparate systems for effective sharing within the unified dataspace. Used tools should provide new insight, such as gathering client profiles and usage statistics, which will also enable a better understanding of how stakeholders interact with the datasets, supporting continuous improvements.

Data in the Pontus-X ecosystem is shared in a decentralized manner. Rather than providing direct access, data owners can create metadata (data descriptions) and share it within the network. Only those with the appropriate permissions or those who have paid for access can view the data.

The first step involves creating a wallet to interact with the portal, for which MetaMask can be used. Next, it is necessary to connect to the appropriate blockchain network and fund the wallet with resources.

Data access is managed through smart contracts, allowing users to set conditions for access, such as licensing terms, access fees, duration of availability, and specific users permitted to access the data. To share or purchase data, users must cover network transaction fees. When purchasing, currency is exchanged for an access token, enabling access to data per the terms set by the data owner.

Pontus-X ecosystem enables user management and access control mechanisms allowing secure, role-based access, ensuring that users have appropriate permissions aligned with their needs. Standardized descriptions and quality statistics for each dataset will enhance searchability, enabling stakeholders to evaluate datasets by quality and other critical metrics. This approach will also simplify the process of exploring data based on specific criteria, such as data quality.

The initial set of datasets to be included in the dataspace consists of eDWIN agriculture vocabularies, agrometeorological data, pest and disease alerts, and Agrego's food production statistics. Planned sources of the data:

- eDWIN Weather Data
Provides data from about 550 stations since 2019, including key information on temperature, rainfall humidity, and wind speed.
- eDWIN Agriculture Statistics Data
Provides aggregated data in agricultural production from selected areas over certain years
- eDWIN Plant pests and disease data
Offers images and summaries of plant growth stages and pest activities, helping with better management of crops and pests.
- eDWIN Near Real-Time Data
Includes live monitoring of plant and livestock in agricultural fields using PTZ cameras.
- eDWIN Species Identification Data

- Contains taxonomic information from domain institutes, aiding in the identification of plant and animal species.
- eDWIN Pest and Disease Models Data
Offers results from disease risk models and crops, helping with early detection and risk management
- Agrego Food Production Statistics
External datasets in food production domain provide aggregated data from production from selected areas over certain years.

Progress has already been made in preparing the system's architecture, gathering data sources, and initiating AIM integration. Building the AIM environment and services will expedite data exchange, enhance interoperability, and shorten the data-sharing process, fostering stronger integration within the agriculture sector. Utilizing tools to align data with AIM standards will further ensure seamless integration and operability across diverse systems.

The public instance of the Pontus-X based instance of the Polish agriculture dataspace is available via:
<https://dataspaces.psnc.pl/>

Conclusions

This deliverable illustrates progress that was made during the second year of execution of AgrifoodTEF with regards to dataspace implementation. In particular, it presents two approaches that are most mature at the time of writing in terms of code availability: one based on open-source components under development by projects such as Eclipse Data Space Components (EDC) and Eclipse XFSC, and the other using Pontus-X, a commercial platform that produces open source code enabling independent deployments.

Both approaches are providing support for sovereign data-sharing, giving the possibility of programmatically aggregating usage policies for access. In both cases there is also availability of code, but the Pontus-X approach proposes a more concrete data space implementation with "built-in data monetisation" rather than having to build a separate one from scratch, while addressing also the need for harmonized data standards and shared governance.

In this deliverable, we have illustrated some key aspects which will be part of the AgrifoodTEF dataspace for the following reasons:

- Technologies used: AgrifoodTEF has decided to adopt Pontus-X for its compute-to-data capabilities and Gaia-X for compliance and interoperability. These enable secure data exchanges while preserving data owner control.
- Implementation Framework: Dataspace supports publishing datasets and algorithms through a user-friendly interface exposing de-facto a data marketplace. It enforces usage policies, facilitates secure transactions, and ensures data traceability through distributed ledger technology (DLT).
- Stakeholder Benefits: Farmers and data originators retain control of their data while enabling researchers and industry players to access processed insights. This enhances trust promotes wider participation.

- Use Cases: The implementation of use cases, such as data-sharing in the pig sector, demonstrates its ability to reduce barriers through sovereign data-sharing models. Algorithms can analyse data without transferring ownership, exemplifying privacy-by-design.

A roadmap for the future implementations can be foreseen for the short-term and long-term. Short-term goals include providing the project partners with guidelines, finalizing the integration of existing technologies and deploying pilot use cases to validate functionality and usability of dataspace functionality. The use of proposed technologies, widely recognised as leading initiatives at European level, brings additional harmonisation opportunities that feeds our long-term vision.

This includes enriching the dataspace with the contributions of TEF customers willing to explore monetisation opportunities, while integrating it with other European agricultural and non-agricultural data-sharing initiatives, focusing on scaling operations and fostering partnerships across sectors that contribute to a growing data economy.

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